

Application of 2-carboxy-2',4'-diamino azo benzene dye in jute dyeing

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Abstract : In the present study 2-carboxy-2',4'-diamino azo benzene dye is synthesized by diazo coupling of anthranilic acid with *m*-phenylenediamine which has been applied on jute fabric under three different dyeing condition like neutral, alkaline and acidic pH using conventional jute dyeing process at boil. Considering the colour yield and washing fastness property, dyeing of jute fabric in acidic condition is found to exhibit best results.

Keywords : Azo-benzene dye, jute dyeing.

Jute, a natural biodegradable fibre had a tremendous application in packing industries but its utility is reducing day by day. Decreasing trend in the use of jute fibre in the traditional sector like packaging is being well compensated by the increasing use of jute in diversified sector. Jute is now finding its use in several diversified application like curtains, baggage and even in apparel sectors. So the wet processing of jute has occupied a very important position in jute industry as the diversified products needs good look and attractive feel where bleaching, dyeing, finishing etc. of jute is a must. A number of work has been carried out in the field of bleaching, dyeing etc. like energy saving ambient temperature bleaching simultaneous operation of several process reuse of bleach as well as dye bath, bleaching will different bleaching agents, dyeing with several class of dyes etc.¹. Due to these effects jute products with attractive look can be made with different option and processes of the product with bright shade. Fastness of properties also is required. We can go for vat or reactive dyeing on hydrogen peroxide bleached fabric. But for the production of cheap products with moderate to low fastness properties we go for acid, basic, direct dyes etc. So, the product can be produced depending on the end use requirement. Mostly the dyes suitable for cellulosic fibre dyeing are used for dyeing of jute with process and method modification. No work has been done for the synthesis of a dyestuff in a simple way for dyeing of jute following conventional dyeing method. So, in this study a dye has been synthesized which has azo group as chromophore and carboxyl and amino group as auxochrome. The synthesized dye has been applied on jute fabric by conventional hot dyeing process using different dye bath pH to standardise a process. The dye has been characterized and the dyed jute fibre has also been evaluated.

Experimental

Fabric : A plain weave grey jute fabric having following specification was used; Warp : 67 ends/dcm (count, 147 tex); Weft : 67 ends/dcm (count, 147 tex); Fabric mass : 205 gms/sq.m (at 65% RH and 20 °C)

The following chemicals were used for the preparation of dyestuff 2-carboxy-2,4-diamino azo benzene : anthranilic acid, *m*-phenylenediamine, conc. acetic acid (17 *N*), sodium nitrite, sodium acetate

The following A.R. grade chemicals were used for bleaching and dyeing purpose. Hydrogen peroxide, trisodium phosphate, sodium hydroxide, sodium carbonate, sodium silicate, sodium sulphate, sodium acetate, non-ionic detergent (Ultravon JU) and acetic acid

Preparation of dye (synthesis of a new azo dye 2-carboxy-2',4'-diamino azo benzene)

13.7 g of anthranilic acid was dissolved in 200 ml of dil. acetic acid solution containing 100 ml of conc. acetic acid. The solution was cooled in a freezing mixture and diazotised with the drop-wise addition of cooled solution (0 °C) of sodium nitrite (6.5 g). Keeping the temperature at 0–5 °C, the diazotised product was added slowly to a cooled (0–5 °C) alkaline solution of *m*-phenylenediamine (12 g), dissolved in 16 g of sodium acetate. The resultant mixture was acidified with 5(*N*) acetic acid when brilliant red dye was obtained. It was filtered through suction, washed thoroughly with double distilled water, till free from alcohol. The yield of dye obtained 18.8 g showing 80% conversion.

Bleaching of jute fabric : Conventional bleaching of

grey jute fabric was performed in a closed vessel containing H_2O_2 (2 vol.), TSP (1 g/L), NaOH (g/L), sodium silicate (10 g/L) and nonionic detergent (2 g/L) for 2 h at 90 °C with a material to liquor ratio of 1 : 20. After bleaching, the fibre samples were washed, neutralised with acetic acid (2 ml/L), washed again and dried.

Dyeing of bleached jute fabric : Bleached jute fabrics were dyed separately in three different conditions : (A) in neutral pH, (B) in alkaline pH and (C) in acidic pH. Bleached jute fabrics were first entered in the dye bath containing dye (4%, w/v), glaubersalt (20 g/L) using material to liquor ratio of 1 : 10 at different pH. The temperature was then raised slowly at 80 °C and dyeing continued at the temperature for 1 h. After dyeing the samples were washed thoroughly in cold water and then soaped at boil for 15 min, using 1 : 10 material to liquor ratio and 2 g/L detergent. The samples were then washed thoroughly with water and dried in air.

Determination of the physico-chemical properties :

All the reactive dyed jute fibre samples were subjected to wash fastness tests in a Launder-O-Meter as per IS : 3361-1979. Wash fastness ratings of all the dyed jute fibre samples were evaluated with the help of computer colour matching system. Whiteness index in the 'HUNTER' scale, yellowness index in the 'ASTM D 1925' scale and Brightness index in the 'TAPPI 45' scale of grey and processed jute fibre samples were measured by the Spectrascan-5100 © computer colour matching system using relevant softwares. Spectrascan-5100 © computer colour matching system was also used to measure λ_{max} reflectance and *K/S* values of different dyed jute fabric samples using relevant softwares and following formula :

$$K/S = [(1 - R)^2/2R]\alpha C$$

where *K*, is the coefficient of absorption; *S*, the coefficient of scattering; *R*, the reflectance of substrate at λ_{max} ; and *C*, the concentration of dye. The *K/S* value is viewed as an index of dye uptake.

Results and discussion

Structural elucidation of 2-carboxy-2',4'-diamino azo benzene :

The azo-dye has been synthesized by diazotization of anthranilic acid followed by coupling with alkaline solution of *m*-phenylenediamine². The elemental analysis data {percentage found; (Calcd.)} C, 60.94 (61.00); H, 4.69 (4.70); N, 21.88 (21.92). The band characterisation of the dye was done in detail using IR-technique³.

2938 cm^{-1} (aromatic $-\text{NH}_2$ stretching frequency), 1607 cm^{-1} (aromatic $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ stretching frequency), 1386 cm^{-1}

(aromatic $-\text{COOH}$ stretching frequency for $\gamma_{\text{C-O}}$ (sym)), 1451 cm^{-1} (aromatic $-\text{COOH}$ stretching frequency for $\gamma_{\text{C-O}}$ (assym)).

The dye is soluble in water due to the presence of $-\text{COOH}$ group and also have affinity towards the jute fibre due to the presence of two amino group. The dye has an azo group as chromophore while one carboxyl and two amino group as auxochrome.

Due to the presence of the chromophore and auxochrome group the compound can be treated as dye for textile application. The spectral absorbances are : 300 nm ($\epsilon = 9130$); 478 ($\epsilon = 11410$).

The whiteness, yellowness and brightness indices are 53.99, 46.21, 23.96 and 83.17, 18.82, 64.59 respectively for the grey and the bleached fabrics at 10 ° angle of observation.

Bleached jute fabric has been dyed with the manufactured dye at three different pH condition keeping the other parameters like dye concentration, salt concentration, time, temperature etc. constant. The colour yield in terms of *K/S* value is maximum i.e. 8.404 in acidic medium and colour yield is very poor in alkaline condition while it is medium i.e. 4.892 if dyeing is carried out neutral bath. Wash fastness is found to be good i.e. 4 (following was fastness scale of 1–5) for dyed samples produced in acid bath.

Conclusion : The manufactured dye contains azo group as chromophore and carboxyl and amino groups as auxochrome. The dye is cationic in nature. The derived dye can be used for dyeing of jute fabric in acidic condition as a basic dye.

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